

How to Watch Videos with Subtitles in Your Language

Local Food Advisors' Journey 2026 - EU4Advice & COREnet

Welcome! All videos from the Local Food Advisors' Journey campaign include English subtitles that can be automatically translated into your preferred language. Follow these simple steps to activate subtitles in your own language.

Step 1: Activate Closed Captions (CC)

Click on the **CC button** (Closed Captions) located at the bottom right corner of the video player to turn on subtitles.

Step 2: Open Settings

Click on the **Settings** icon next to the CC button at the bottom right of the video player.

Step 3: Select Subtitles/CC

In the settings menu that appears, click on **Subtitles/CC**. You will see the current subtitle language (English - United Kingdom).

Step 4: Choose Auto-translate

Click on **Auto-translate** at the bottom of the subtitle options menu. This will open a list of available languages.

Step 5: Select Your Language

Scroll through the language list and click on **your preferred language**. The subtitles will automatically switch to your selected language.

Note: YouTube's auto-translation feature supports over 100 languages. While the automatic translation may not be perfect, it provides a helpful way to understand the content in your native language. The original English subtitles have been carefully reviewed for accuracy.